

FACTORS OF ORIGIN OF FAMILY VIOLENCE IN UZBEKISTAN, EFFECTIVENESS OF EXISTING LEGAL FRAMEWORKS IN COMBATING FAMILY VIOLENCE

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Abstract. This article expresses some factors of origin of family violence in Uzbekistan, effectiveness of existing legal frameworks in combating family violence.

Key words: family violence, global agenda, legal frameworks.

Family violence cannot be justified under any circumstances, because it affects the basic rights of a person (life, health, honor, dignity, freedom). Violence can be manifested not only by the use of physical force, but also in the form of mental, moral, economic and domestic pressure and can be applied to any member of the family. Insulting, coercion, rape, economic restrictions, regular mental torture are also considered as violence. The law protects citizens from any kind of violence.

The term "family violence" is not defined in the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan. But at the international level, this term is widely used. Domestic violence is not only a disease of one country and nation, the whole world is struggling with it. Therefore, we quote the definition from international sources.

Family-domestic violence is regular, repeated violence against one member of the family by another member or members, and it mainly occurs within the family. It can manifest itself in the form of physical, mental, sexual and economic violence.

If you look at the global statistics and general trends, it becomes clear that women and children are the main victims of domestic violence. But this is not absolute, that is, in the family, it is observed that a man also lives under the pressure of his wife or parents from children or other family members. This is also a form of family violence. Because, in this case, the primary rights of the person are violated,

as a result, the victim may develop serious psychosomatic diseases or other unfortunate situations may occur.

Protecting the rights and legal interests of women in the country, increasing their economic, social and political activity, maintaining their health, providing vocational training and employment, wide involvement in entrepreneurship, social support of needy women -support, systematic continuation of the ongoing reforms to ensure gender equality, as well as consistent implementation of the Sustainable Development Goals of the United Nations Global Agenda:

- Women who have continuous work experience for the last 6 months in all legal entities, except budget organizations, are paid pregnancy and maternity allowance from the State budget, based on the amount of minimum consumption expenses for each month;
- 50 percent of the monthly rent paid by them, but not more than 500,000 soums the remaining part should be covered from the funds of the "Women's Notebook" fund, the republican budget of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the local budgets of the regions and the city of Tashkent.
- increasing responsibility for intentionally causing physical injury to a woman who is a close relative;
- establishing criminal liability for disclosing information that reflects the confidential aspects of a person's life, derogatory to honor and dignity;
- to ensure the preparation and broadcasting of TV programs under the column "Women's Success" that promote virtues such as modesty, chastity, patience and the pursuit of knowledge about women who have achieved success in various fields.

When looking at the reasons, one should not ignore the characteristics of the mentality. In Uzbek families, private life and family secrets are sacred, and our nation is considered very concertive in this sense. In short, in most cases, domestic violence does not go outside the family. Uzbek families are usually multi-member, that is, not only husband and wife, but also their relatives play an important role in

the chain of relationships. Mother-in-law, father-in-law and other relatives oppress the daughter-in-law in the family, they want her to obey unconditionally, not to demand any privileges, or parents put pressure on the child, and daughters-in-law put pressure on the sick mother-in-law or father-in-law. Unfortunately, in most cases, these situations cause the victim to commit suicide or endure oppression until reaching the last, critical point, receive serious physical injuries, mental shocks, and irreparably lose their health. In addition, there are situations in the society of not interfering in someone's internal affairs, thinking about one's own peace, indifference to the problem, and tolerance. When family violence gets out of control and the problem becomes bigger, the appeals are often quickly closed by the precinct supervisor or the community meeting, the reasons are not investigated, and they are limited to temporary measures that apply only to that situation. As a result, the problem becomes deeper rooted.

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